

Studies in the Cotarnine Series. Part III. Isomeric *bis*-Cotarnino-acetones.

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It has been explained in the previous papers that two structures are possible for the products of condensation of cotarnine with compounds containing the reactive methylene group, such as acetone, acetophenone, etc., according as they are viewed as derivatives of the aldehyde or the carbinol forms in the tautomeric system of which cotarnine is composed. Although all attempts to prepare such derivatives of these compounds as would furnish clear proofs of one structure or the other had hitherto failed or led to inconclusive results, the reinvestigation of the condensation of cotarnine and acetone which was originally studied by Liebermann and Kropf (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 211) has led to very interesting results and enabled us to isolate both the possible isomeric forms.

Liebermann condensed cotarnine with acetone using sodium carbonate as the condensing agent but no solvent, and obtained a crystalline product (m.p. 83°), of which the hydrochloride (m.p. 171°), the benzoyl derivative (m.p. 124°), and the methiodide designated by him 'anhydromethyl cotarnino-acetone methylate' (m.p. 144°), were prepared. We have been able to confirm these observations except with regard to the methiodide, which is found to melt at 168° and from which a nitrogen-free product, *bis*-cotarnonideneacetone (VI) has been prepared in a somewhat impure condition by steaming its mixture with alkali.

Liebermann assumed that in this reaction one molecule each of cotarnine and acetone had condensed and that it might be a derivative of the aldehyde or the carbinol form.

Careful analyses and determinations of molecular weight have shown, however, that the product should be regarded as dicotarnyldeneacetone (I), two molecules of cotarnine having reacted with one molecule of acetone:

This is in agreement with the observations made by Pyman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 93, 1268, 1740) who obtained a similar product by condensing acetone with the aldehyde prepared from laudanosine by oxidation with manganese dioxide and sulphuric acid.

The significant observation has now been made by us that if this condensation with acetone be effected *in presence of alcohol* using, as before, sodium carbonate solution as the condensing agent, an entirely different but isomeric product (II) melting at 150-51° is obtained. The latter compound dissolves in dilute acids without any decomposition but is not acted upon by acetic anhydride, benzoyl chloride or phenyl isocyanate. The absence of the secondary imino-group is thus indicated. It forms a different methiodide (III) m.p. 210°, which, on treatment with alkali and steaming, gives *N*-methyldicotarnylideneacetone (IV). The latter compound reacted with fresh methyl iodide, the resulting methiodide (V, m.p. 168°) being found to be identical with Liebermann's 'anhydro-methylcotarninoacetone methylate' and to yield with alkali the same nitrogen-free product (II).

The new product (m.p. 151°) should evidently be assigned, therefore, the cyclic constitution (IV).

It would be seen, therefore, that in the case of acetone two isomeric compounds (I) and (II) may be obtained by working under different conditions. The view that the change of the aldehyde into the carbinol phase has been effected by the solvent is strikingly supported by the observation that the unsaturated compound (I), m.p. 83° , is rapidly and quantitatively converted into the saturated one (II), m.p. 151° , by crystallisation from hot alcohol.

Several attempts made to differentiate between the two isomers in the case of the other condensation products, *e.g.* with acetophenone, etc., have hitherto been unsuccessful, the stable isoquinoline derivative being the only recognisable product of the reaction. This is undoubtedly due to the remarkable tendency of the imino-hydrogen to migrate to the aldehydic carbon atom, any attempts at preparing derivatives resulting in the closure of the isoquinoline ring. Thus Liebermann's compound (m.p. 83°), on treatment with cold acetic anhydride, is found to be converted not into the expected acetyl derivative, but into the isomer (m.p. 151°). The reaction is best explained by assuming the formation of an intermediate acetyl compound which is immediately hydrolysed by water as follows:—

The acceptance of these views would make the mechanism of the reaction of cotarnine with compounds of the type of resorcinol in which the keto-enol change is known to occur so readily and also with other compounds containing reactive methylene groups, at once intelligible. The condensation, if effected in the presence of non-ionising solvents, *e.g.*, benzene, is assumed to occur with the aldehyde group, but in most cases the mobility of the imino-hydrogen atom causes the intermediate unsaturated products to be so unstable that ring-closure follows almost immediately with the formation of *N*-methyl tetrahydro-isoquinoline derivatives. The case of the acetone condensation product provides the only exception in which the unsaturated compound is found to be sufficiently stable to permit of its isolation and study. The following scheme should, therefore, represent the course of all condensations of this type occurring between ketomethylene compounds and cotarnine:—

EXPERIMENTAL.

bis-Cotarninoacetone (II).—Cotarnine (5 g.) and acetone (2 c.c.) were mixed with 25 c. c. of absolute alcohol, a small amount of anhydrous sodium carbonate added and the clear solution kept at laboratory temperature for 2 days. On pouring the liquid into water an oil was precipitated which, on rubbing and keeping in contact with water for 24 hours, completely solidified. It was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid, reprecipitated with ammonia and then crystallised from hot dilute alcohol as colourless crystals, m. p. 150-51°, yield 8.5 g.

It dissolved in cold acetone and benzene but more sparingly in alcohol. A sparingly soluble hydrochloride separated from its solution in cold 4 N-HCl, m. p. 167° (decomp.) [Found: C, 64.77; H, 6.5; N, 5.19; M. W. (ebulliscope in acetone), 516. $C_{27}H_{32}O_7N_2$ requires C, 65.32; H, 6.45; N, 5.62 per cent. M. W. 496]. (Found: Cl, 11.98. $C_{27}H_{32}O_7N_2$, 2 HCl requires Cl, 12.50 per cent).

bis-Cotarninoisopropyl alcohol.—The previous compound (1 g.) was dissolved in a slight excess of dilute hydrochloric acid and the calculated amount of freshly prepared sodium amalgam (2.5%) was added in small quantities at a time. The mixture was shaken well and left overnight. The clear supernatant solution was then decanted from the mercury and basified with 2% alkali when the product separated as an oil which quickly solidified. It was washed with water and purified by dissolving in dilute acids and reprecipitating with alkali. A colourless crystalline solid, m. p. 108° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{27}H_{34}O_7N_2$ requires N, 5.60 per cent).

bis-Cotarninoacetone methiodide.—On rubbing the acetone compound with a slight excess of methyl iodide a clear solution resulted and from this the crystalline methiodide separated almost immediately. Crystallisation from a large volume of hot water gave small yellow rod-shaped crystals melting at 210°. The crystals contained a molecule of water of crystallisation which was lost on drying at 110°/5 mm. over P_2O_5 . [Found: H_2O (dried at 110°/5mm.), 3.77; I, 30.25. $C_{29}H_{38}O_7N_2I_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires H_2O , 4.42; I, 31.11 per cent].

N-methyl-bis-cotarnylideneacetone.—A solution of the methiodide in hot water was treated with excess of 20% alkali. A yellow precipitate which soon changed into an oil separated, and the characteristic fishy odour of methylamine was also perceived. The mixture was boiled, cooled and the red oil extracted with chloroform. The semi-solid mass, left on evaporation of the chloroform, dissolved completely in cold dilute hydrochloric acid and the solution quickly deposited the *hydrochloride* as a mass of crystals which were recrystallised from a little hot water, m.p. 181-82° (decomp.). There was no loss of weight on drying the hydrochloride at 110°/5 mm. (Found: Cl, 13.0. $C_{29}H_{36}O_7N_2$, 2HCl, requires Cl, 12.22 per cent).

The *platinichloride* was also prepared and analysed. (Found: Pt, 19.51. $C_{29}H_{36}O_7N_2$, 2HCl, Pt Cl₄ requires Pt, 20.89 per cent).

N-methyl-bis-cotarnylideneacetone methiodide.—On stirring the oily base with methyl iodide, there was a vigorous reaction with considerable evolution of heat and the oil changed into a mass of bright yellow crystals. Recrystallisation from dilute alcohol furnished

small yellow needles, m.p. 168° (decomp.), not depressed by admixture with the product prepared directly from (I). The crystals dried at room temperature were found to contain water of crystallisation which was lost on drying at $78^{\circ}/5$ mm. over P_2O_5 . [Found: H_2O , (dried at $78^{\circ}/5$ mm.), 3.88; I, 29.10. $C_{31}H_{42}O_7N_2I_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires H_2O , 4.26; I, 30.08 per cent]. [Found (in material dried at 78° in vacuum): C, 46.9; H, 5.41. $C_{31}H_{42}O_7N_2I_2$ requires C, 46.05; H, 5.2 per cent].

bis-Cotarnonideneacetone.—The above mentioned methiodide was dissolved in hot water, excess of caustic soda added and the mixture distilled in steam. Trimethylamine was formed and was identified in the distillate by its picrate, m.p. 216° . On cooling, the yellow oil was extracted with ether and the dried ethereal solution evaporated. The cotarnonideneacetone was left as a yellow oil which solidified to a reddish mass on standing for two days. The product was proved to be free from nitrogen but could not be obtained in a sufficiently pure condition for analysis.

bis-Cotarnylideneacetone, identical with anhydrocotarninoacetone of Liebermann and Kropf (*loc. cit.*) (I). A suspension of finely powdered cotarnine (1 g.) in acetone (10 c.c.) was treated with 2 c.c. of 4*N*-sodium carbonate solution and the mixture shaken vigorously when the cotarnine gradually dissolved. After 6 hours the excess of acetone was removed on the water-bath and the residual oil left overnight when it solidified to a hard gritty mass. It was washed with cold water and dried on the porous plate. The crude product weighed more than 1 g. and melted at 74° - 76° . Crystallisation from acetone gave colourless prisms, m.p. 83° .

Conversion of bis-cotarnylideneacetone (I) into bis-cotarninoacetone (II).—A solution of I (1 g.) in the minimum amount of rectified spirit was heated to 50° on the water-bath for 15 minutes and left overnight. On adding water the solution became milky and an oil separated which slowly hardened on rubbing. This was redissolved in alcohol, warmed and after 12 hours the solution diluted with water when the oil changed quickly into a mass of colourless crystals (0.9 g.) which, after drying in vacuum, melted at 150 - 51° , not depressed by admixture with (II).

Action of methyl iodide on (I).—The product (V), m.p. 168° , was identified with the methiodide obtained from (II) in two stages, and was decomposed by boiling alkali into *bis-cotarnonideneacetone* and trimethylamine.